

PHOTOTROPY AND PHOTOCHEMICAL ISOMERISM FROM THE MAGNETIC STANDPOINT.

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Magnetic properties of some phototropic and photoisomeric compounds have been investigated. The distinct change in the magnetic susceptibility value of cinnamylidene-malononic acid and thiophosgene observed on exposure to light, has been ascribed to the formation of a polymer and that of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to the formation of an isomer. No effect on the magnetic susceptibility value of anils and hydrazones has been observed on exposure to light. On the basis of the magnetic data obtained, the view of Senier and Shepherd, that the change in colour of anils and hydrazones on exposure to light is due to the change in the aggregation, has been favoured, and other theories put forth to account for the mechanism of phototropy have been discussed.

Much speculation is rife as regards the nature of transformations which take place when a substance undergoes a phototropic change. This change is completely or partially reversible when the exposed substances are kept in the dark for a sufficiently long time, heated or recrystallised. Marckwald (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, **30**, 140) from the phototropic behaviour of α -tetrachloro-*o*-ketonaphthalene concluded that the phenomenon was a purely physical one, bound up with the crystal form of the substance. Senier and Shepherd (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 441, 1943), as a result of the study of a large number of anils, hydrazones and fulgides considered the phototropic change simply as being due to 'the existence of complex solid molecular aggregates related to gaseous molecules as gaseous molecules are related to atoms.' It is implied that different aggregates have different colours. Chemical theories suggesting the formation of new compounds on exposure to light have been put forth. But all of these suffer from the handicap that no one has been able to isolate or identify or even conclusively show the existence of the hypothetical new compound formed by light. The authors have undertaken to examine the mechanism of phototropy from the changes in magnetic properties which should take place when either a new compound is formed or when polymerisation takes place in a compound or when there is a change in crystal structure on exposure to light.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Compounds.—The anils and hydrazones were prepared by condensing the aldehydes with amines and hydrazines respectively

(Emmerich, *Annalen*, 1887, 241, 351; Senier and Shepherd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1943; Biltz, *Annalen*, 1899, 308, 170). The crude condensed product was recrystallised from suitable solvents till the melting point of the compound prepared was in agreement with that given in literature.

Cinnamylidene-malonic acid was prepared according to the method of Rüber (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2411).

Thiophosgene was prepared according to the method of Frankland and Garner (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1920, 39, 3147). It was kept over calcium chloride and boiled at 75°. It is a red liquid turning to a white crystalline product on exposure to light. The white compound separated and recrystallised from light petroleum melted at 117°. The previously reported m.p. is 116-119° (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 567).

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde.—Kahlbaum's extra pure compound was recrystallised from benzene.

Maleic Acid.—Kahlbaum's extra pure maleic acid was recrystallised from an aqueous solution and dried at 100°.

All these compounds, after properly drying and testing their purity by comparing their melting points and colour changes on exposure to light with those given in literature, were stored in glass tubes wrapped with black paper and were placed in a vacuum desiccator till further use.

For magnetic investigations, the magnetic susceptibility was determined on the Bhatnagar-Mathur Interference balance (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, vii, 8, 1041) manufactured by Adam Hilger, Ltd., London and the Gouy's balance. The compound was then exposed to light in a vacuum desiccator. The mass was thoroughly raked at regular intervals in order to enable a uniform colour change to take place in the whole bulk of the compound. The magnetic susceptibility of the coloured modification was then determined. It was kept in darkness or was heated to a suitable temperature to recover its original colour. The magnetic susceptibility of the compound was again determined. These processes were repeated on the same compound at least thrice and the mean of a large number of readings for each modification was taken. It was found in all the cases that the magnetic susceptibility value of the compound after the recovery of the colour of the exposed sample was almost identical with the original one.

The results of such measurements of magnetic susceptibility of the compounds both before and after exposure to light are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Name of the compound.	$\chi \times 10^7$.	
	Original.	After exposure.
1. Thiophosgene	-4.40 $\bar{x}$ (liquid)	-3.914 (solid)
2. Cinnamylidene-malonic acid	-4.835	-4.140
3. Maleic acid	-4.283	-4.280
4. β -Naphthylamine-salicylidene :		
(i) Yellow variety	-5.394	-5.389
(ii) Red variety	-5.394	-5.393
5. <i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid-salicylidene	-5.070	-5.070
6. <i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid ethyl ester salicylidene	-5.900	-5.903
7. <i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine-salicylidene :		
(i) Needle crystals	-4.195	-4.193
(ii) Plate crystals	-4.782	-4.783
8. <i>m</i> -Toluidine-salicylidene	-4.965	-4.966
9. <i>o</i> -Anisidine-salicylidene	-5.792	-5.790
10. Benzaldehyde-phenylhydrazone	-6.065	-6.075
11. Benzaldehyde- <i>p</i> -bromophenylhydrazone	-5.465	-5.467
12. 5-Bromosalicyldehyde-diphenylhydrazone	-5.465	-5.467
13. Benzaldehyde- <i>p</i> -tolylhydrazone	-6.342	-6.342
14. Anisaldehyde-phenylhydrazone	-6.090	-6.088
15. Cinnamyldehyde-phenylhydrazone	-5.872	-5.872
16. Cinnamyldehyde- <i>p</i> -bromophenylhydrazone	-5.381	-5.380
17. Cinnamyldehyde- <i>p</i> -tolylhydrazone	-6.184	-6.185
18. Cinnamyldehyde- β -naphthylhydrazone	-4.066	-4.066
19. Vanillin- β -naphthylhydrazone	-6.011	-6.014
20. Benzilphenylhydrazone	-6.080	-6.080
21. Benzil- <i>o</i> -tolylhydrazone	-6.353	-6.354
22. Piperonal- <i>p</i> -tolylhydrazone	-5.833	-5.832
23. Piperonal- β -naphthylhydrazone	-4.962	-4.962

In the case of cinnamylidene-malonic acid it was observed, however, that on exposure to light in the presence of air and moisture at 50-60°, the sample did not give repeatable magnetic susceptibility values. The values observed on several occasions were even higher than those of the unexposed sample. It was, therefore, necessary to expose cinnamylidene-malonic acid in vacuum at low temperatures.

The variation observed in the magnetic susceptibility value of the cinnamylidene-malonic acid observed on exposure to light at 50-60° in presence of air and moisture may be due to the formation of some oxidised products of polymerised compounds. The final magnetic susceptibility value of the exposed sample in vacuum, therefore, may not be the value for the polymerised product alone, but it may be the value at the equilibrium point of the various products formed.

It was found during experimentation that *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde melted when exposed in a desiccator to direct sunlight and a solution of alum had to be employed to cut off the heat rays.

The compound first turned green but after a few hours it became whitish and after a few days it changed completely into a white mass. The compound was raked from time to time and the magnetic susceptibilities determined are shown in Table II.

Solution of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in acetone when exposed to light turns green and after some time a white compound begins to separate out of the solution. The magnetic susceptibility in solution at three various stages has been determined and the results are shown in Table III.

TABLE II.

For o-nitrobenzaldehyde.

Time of exposure.	Colour.	$\chi \times 10^7$.
0 hour	Yellow	-4.398
12 hours	Greenish yellow	-4.430
36	Greenish yellow (white)	-4.295
50	Greenish yellow and white crystals	-4.267
96	White and slightly greenish	-4.135
6 days	White	-3.993
8 days		-3.930
	<i>o</i> -Nitrosobenzoic acid	-3.926

TABLE III.

Magnetic susceptibility of o-nitrobenzaldehyde in acetone solution.

Susceptibility of acetone = -5.830×10^{-7} .

Time of exposure.	Colour.	$\chi \times 10^7$.
5 minutes	10% Solution	-4.401
10	Green solution	-4.430
60	White nitrosobenzoic acid started separating out	-4.158

DISCUSSION.

Prominent points which are brought out from the data given above are that on exposure to light :

(a) there is a distinct change in the magnetic susceptibility of cinnamylidene-malonic acid, thiophosgene and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde ;

(b) there is no effect on the magnetic susceptibility in the case of maleic acid, hydrazones and anils.

Cinnamylidene-malonic Acid.—Rüber (*loc. cit.*) showed that the yellow cinnamylidene-malonic acid on exposure to light polymerises and is transformed to a colourless acid which is a dimeride diphenyltetramethyl-dicarboxylic acid.

Now as a result of the polymerisation of cinnamylidene-malonic acid, the mass susceptibility of the acid should rise as it polymerises, as polymerisation results in the disappearance of two double bonds. Instead of a rise however, there is a fall. This seems to be probably due to the formation of a ring on polymerisation according to equation (i). An analogous behaviour has been reported by Farquharson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 219) in the case of the polymerisation of *cyclopentadiene*, where too the disappearance of the double bonds and the formation of the ring results in a fall rather than in a rise of mass susceptibility.

Thiophosgene.—Schonberg and Stephenson (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 567) showed that thiophosgene on exposure to light forms a white solid photodimer. Schonberg (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 574), suggested the appearance of diradical (II) during the process of photodimerisation and assigned constitution (III) to the photodimer.

If a diradical be formed as suggested by Schonberg, the liquid after exposure to light should show paramagnetism. Even if in the photoequilibrium the concentration of the diradical be small, it should be capable of being detected magnetically, because of the strong paramagnetism that a biradical should exhibit. But actually the value of the exposed liquid was found to be -4.394×10^{-7} which is practically identical with the value for unexposed thiophosgene (-4.401×10^{-7}). From this the probable conclusion is that the suggested diradical is not formed or if it is formed its life is so short that it is incapable of being detected magnetically.

From the magnetic data given in Table I, we find that on exposure to light, the magnetic susceptibility value of thiophosgene falls from -4.401×10^{-7} to -3.914×10^{-7} . A change in the magnetic susceptibility does take place when a liquid solidifies but as a general rule the magnetic susceptibility rises when this happens. The only other explanation of this change is polymerisation. The polymerisation of thiophosgene on exposure to light is

accompanied by the disappearance of two double bonds between C:S and by the formation of a ring. A fall of the magnetic susceptibility observed may be due to the disappearance of double bonds, but this would result in a rise rather than a fall in the value. The fall may be attributed, therefore, to the formation of a closed ring analogous to that of cinnamylidene-malonic acid and cyclopentadiene.

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde.—The effect of sunlight on *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde was first studied by Ciamician and Silber (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2040). Since then this phenomenon has been investigated extensively both in the solid state as well as in solution and it has been shown that on exposure to light this substance is transformed into *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid. Lobry de Bruyn (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1903, 22, 298) and later on Bowen and his collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1218) while studying this phenomenon suggested that during the process of transformation of aldehyde to the acid, the green compound that is formed is the monomolecular variety, whereas the white acid that is formed ultimately is the bimolecular compound.

The magnetic susceptibility value of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, however, is -0.439×10^{-6} and that of *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid -0.3926×10^{-6} . If the magnetic data tabulated in Table II be examined, it would be observed that the magnetic susceptibility of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in the solid state after an exposure of 12 hours is slightly higher (-0.443) than that of the original compound, but on longer exposures it begins to decrease and ultimately after 8 days the value becomes constant at -0.393×10^{-6} , which is the magnetic susceptibility value for *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid. In solution also the value of the green compound is somewhat higher than that of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde after a mild exposure to light. But when white *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid starts to separate out, the magnetic value falls. This suggests, therefore, that the magnetic susceptibility value of the green *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid is higher than that of the white variety. It has been shown that the polymerisation of a compound is accompanied with a change in magnetic susceptibility. The lower magnetic susceptibility value of the white *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid shows therefore that it is a polymer of the green variety as suggested by Bowen and his collaborators. In order to confirm this, the molecular weights of the two varieties were experimentally determined. The white *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid is insoluble in most liquid solvents. Therefore its molecular weight was determined by Rast's method, using camphor as the solvent and was found to be 292 whereas that of the green solution in benzene, by cryoscopic method, was found to be 151. Both from the magnetic and cryoscopic determinations, it can be inferred, therefore, that the green variety of *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid is monomolecular, whereas the white one is the polymerised variety.

Maleic Acid.—Berthelot and Gaudechon ("Travaux Scientifique de D." Berthelot, Paris, 1917) observed that maleic acid on exposure to light is transformed to fumaric acid. Kailan (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 87, 333) while studying this phenomenon, observed that the photochemical state in

the transformation of maleic to fumaric acid contains 75% maleic acid and 25% fumaric acid. If that be so, the theoretical magnetic susceptibility value of the exposed maleic acid would be -0.427×10^{-6} . The difference between the exposed and unexposed maleic acid is so little that it cannot be detected on the magnetic balance (Bhatnagar and Mathur, *Z. Physik*, 1930, 69, 373).

Anils and Hydrazones.—Anils and hydrazones do not show any change in the magnetic susceptibility value on exposure to light. β -Naphthylamine, salicylidene, a lemon yellow compound, on exposure to light becomes red. The red variety is also obtained by crystallising the compound from alcoholic solution. Senier and Shepherd (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the red and the yellow bases, prepared under special conditions, are identical with those obtained by phototropy and they are related to each other as phototrops. From the magnetic data (Table I), it is clear that the magnetic susceptibility value of all the varieties is the same, showing that all of them are perhaps identical in constitution and that the difference in the colours may be due to their states of aggregation being different.

Disalicylidene-*m*-phenylenediamine is dimorphic. Senier, Shepherd and Clark showed that the two forms, plates and needles, are themselves phototropic and unlike β -naphthylamine-salicylidene, the two varieties are not related to each other as phototrops.

The magnetic susceptibilities of the two varieties, plates and needles, are -4.78×10^{-7} and -4.19×10^{-7} respectively. These values are not affected on exposure to light. The difference in magnetic susceptibility of the two varieties is due to the difference in crystal structure. If there had been a transformation of one variety to another on exposure to light, the magnetic susceptibility would have been changed. But as no change is observed on exposure to light, it shows that the two varieties are not related to each other as phototrops; but are themselves individually phototropic. This view is supported by the conclusions arrived at by Senier and Shepherd (*loc. cit.*) from their investigations.

Padoa (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1913, 23, 1500) believes that the phototropic change involves a polymerisation and depolymerisation and that the weakly coloured stable dark stable forms are the drivers of the more strongly coloured light stable forms

This view is obviously not supported by the present investigation of the phototropic anils and hydrazones, for if polymerisation had taken place it would have been accompanied by a change in the magnetic susceptibility of the compound on exposure to light as for example in the case of anthracene, thiophosgene, cinnamylidene-malonic acid which have been shown to polymerise under the influence of light.

Chattaway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 462) believed that in case of hydrazones, e.g., benzaldehyde-phenylhydrazone, a chemical action takes place and suggested the equilibrium

On the other hand, Gallagher (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1921, iv, 29, 683) synthesised the substance

and found that it was stable both in dark and in light. From this he concluded that phototropy of hydrazones could not be due to the isomeric change as suggested by Chattaway (*loc. cit.*).

As a result of extensive investigations on the phototropy of hydrazones, Craziani and Borini (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1913, 22, 32) suggested the mechanism:

in which they postulated the formation of a hypothetical compound B. On Pascal's additivity law, the magnetic susceptibility of benzaldehyde-phenylhydrazone should be -0.607×10^{-6} and that of compound B should be -0.592×10^{-6} . But actually the magnetic values both for the exposed and the unexposed samples are identical (*vide* Table I). From this it may be concluded that the hypothetical compound is not formed.

This conclusion is, however, open to the criticism that the above noted constancy in the value of the magnetic susceptibility on exposure to light may be due to the formation of a mere trace of the compound B under the circumstances. An experiment was, therefore, devised to cause a considerable amount of change by powdering large crystals to colloidal dimensions, at the same time exposing them to bright light. This resulted in considerable deepening of the colour due to the formation of a sufficient quantity of the supposed photo-isomer, but no change in the magnetic susceptibility value of the powder was noticeable. From this the most probable conclusion that can be drawn is that the compound B is not formed on exposure to light.

The only view which can be supported from the magnetic data is the one put forward by Senier and Shepherd according to which the phototropy of anils and hydrazones is attributed to the change in the aggregates under the action of light, different aggregates having different colours. That a mere change in the aggregate sizes does not cause a change in the value of susceptibility having been fully established by Bhatnagar and his collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 321; *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 78, 9; Lessheim, *Current Sci.*, 1936, 5, 119). It may be suggested, however, that if due to change in aggregate sizes long chain anisotropic molecules are formed, the change in susceptibility may be possible.

A view which has been recently propounded is that the phototropy of anils and hydrazones may be due to the distortion of electronic orbits within a crystal (Lyman Chalkley Jr., *Chem. Rev.*, 1929, 5, 217). The only support for this view at present is that the change in colour in the case of β -naphthylamine-salicylidene can also be brought about by agencies other than light. From the present data no definite conclusion for and against this view can be drawn, although the fact that increasing quantities of coloured materials are formed on colloidalisation of substances only in presence of light, seems to be against the theory of distortion of electronic orbits within the crystal. Further work is in progress.

The authors wish to thank Messrs. Varma and Dhir who were associated with the earlier part of the work but had to give up on account of their employments elsewhere.